

Airborne Wind Energy Certification Roadmap

HAWK

Hibernian Airborne Wind energy Kites

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Executive Summary

This report describes the certification process for conventional wind turbine systems and civil aircraft, with the goal of identifying a roadmap for certification of rigid wing airborne wind energy systems. The report further documents the topics covered by the wind turbine Type Certification process to provide insights into the high-level gaps in the conventional wind energy certification scheme as it would relate to AWE systems.

The report focuses on aerostructures made with fibre-reinforced polymer composites as a key element in AWE systems, which typically require a complex and costly set of validation activities as part of the certification process. The report describes a framework for comparing the certification requirements of both aviation and wind industries, to identify the similarities and gaps for composite components. The framework was applied to three example topics related to aerostructures: choice of fatigue evaluation methodology, temperature effects on composite materials and the design of the blade root attachment. The framework could also be applied more generally as a means of analysing any of the sub-systems or components of an airborne wind energy system for certification.

The next steps from this research include (i) application of the framework to mapping existing standards suitable to AWE sub-systems and components, (ii) continued research to incorporate findings from test/demonstration AWE systems into data-based recommendations for future standards and certification, and (iii) supporting education and training activities on certification for AWE companies as they move towards greater levels of commercial readiness.

1 Introduction

This report meets the deliverable “WP5-D1: Certification Roadmap Report” of the HAWK project. The project proposal provides the following context for the certification analysis for airborne wind energy system aerostructures:

Certification for airborne wind energy systems will require an understanding of the requirements from both civil aviation and conventional wind energy sectors. In the EU, certification of aircraft systems will likely be handled by the EASA and National Aviation Authorities. However, certification of commercial wind energy projects requires approval from bodies such as Det Norske Veritas (DNV). Both industries provide guidance on the design, manufacturing, and maintenance of composite structures, each with industry-specific requirements and guidelines.

In WP5, both industries’ approaches to the certification of composite structures will be reviewed and compared. Deviations between the approaches will be addressed and a roadmap to certification of AWE system airframe structures will be proposed (WP5-D1). The roadmap will contain (i) an overview of the development process, (ii) major deliverables and development milestones and (iii) risks and trade-offs for each industry’s approach.

This report describes the assessment of the aviation and wind industry’s certification processes for composite structures and the development of a certification roadmap for AWES aerostructures.

Chapter 2 describes the background to system certification, and prior work conducted on identifying frameworks for certification for AWES.

Chapter 3 outlines in the overall process for certifying aircraft and wind turbines and sets out the requirements and approvals relevant to AWES.

Chapter 4 describes in greater detail the type certification process for composite structures, identifying the relevant standards and design guidance material for each industry. The chapter also describes a methodology for assessing the differences between both industries’ approaches to composite structure design, manufacturing and testing, concluding with an example gap analysis.

2 The Certification Landscape

Certification is defined as a “third-party attestation related to products, processes, systems or persons”, where the attestation is based on verification of the “fulfilment of specified requirements” [1]. The certification of AWE systems faces several challenges:

1. Both industries (aviation and conventional wind) contain relevant considerations for AWE systems.
2. Both industries have their own requirements, rules and processes for obtaining product and organisational certifications.
3. Both industries have their own supply chains adhering to their rules and regulations.

Figure 1 shows an overview of each certification scheme. For conventional wind energy systems, the IEC System for Certification to Standards Relating to Equipment for Use in Renewable Energy Applications (IECRE) facilitates a global certification system. The IECRE relies on international standards for topics related to safety and equipment performance to create a harmonized certification system. For civil aviation, the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) and the US Federal Aviation Authority (FAA) are the leading certification, regulation and standardisation organisations globally. Within civil aviation, the certification of Unmanned Aircraft Systems (UAS) bears the closest resemblance to airborne wind energy system design and operations, with different requirements to typical manned aircraft.

Figure 1: Overview of each certification scheme, regulations and standards (adapted from [2]).

A survey of eleven AWES developers, conducted for the IEA Wind Task 48, found a common desire to categorize AWES as obstacles for air risk and unmanned aerial systems (UAS) for ground risk, respectively [2]. This would support a more streamlined approach to certification for new AWE systems to help ensure certification requirements are in line with the risks of deploying unmanned aircraft systems.

This could also result in AWES being regulated as obstacles (such as how masts, balloons, etc. are handled), and following the IECRE regulations, with the gaps filled in by application of specific mitigations/standards from the aviation regulations [3]. Figure 2 shows an overview of the resulting potential system of regulations for AWE systems.

Figure 2: AWES goals cross both industries, requiring a delineation of responsibilities and rules.

Currently, certain AWE systems are classed as obstacles from an air risk perspective (like SkySails in Germany), while others require a specific operations risk assessment (SORA), before flight testing can begin (like Kitekraft, Mozaero, Kitepower in Germany, The Netherlands and Ireland respectively). The SORA process defines a risk category for a particular AWES, and as systems grow in size, power output and complexity, their risk classification becomes more stringent.

Figure 3 shows how the risk category for AWES may evolve as they progress from the small-scale pre-commercial stage to large multi-megawatt fully commercial systems. Note the values presented in the figure relate to rigid kite systems, which are the research focus for the HAWK project.

	Pre-Commercial	Early Commercial	Fully Commercial
Wingspan	3 - 8 m	8 - 20 m	20 - 40 m
Mass	< 25 kg	25 - 600 kg	600 - 5670 kg
Airspeed	25 - 50 m/s	25 - 75 m/s	25 - 75 m/s
Configuration	Rigid Wing, Ground-Based Generation, Single Tether	Rigid Wing, Ground-Based Generation, Single Tether	Rigid Wing, Ground-Based Generation, Single Tether
Rated Power	< 50 kW	50 - 100 kW	100 - 2,000 kW
Risk Category	Specific / Open / Other	Specific	Specific / Certified
SAIL Level	II	III	III - V

Figure 3: Risk and maturity levels scale with AWES size, airspeed and power [2].

As systems and the industry mature, certification of one form or another will likely be required for AWE systems. This has led to several groups conducting certification gap analyses, comparing the certification procedures and standards of conventional wind energy and civil aviation.

An example is the ORE Catapult assessment of standardisation and certification in Task 3.3 of the Interreg NWE MegaAWE project [3]. The resulting whitepaper outlines the process of certification of AWES following the steps in the conventional wind industry. It highlights many areas of overlap between the IEC 61400 series of wind turbine design standards and AWES, along with recommendations for developing a certification roadmap.

Figure 4: Review of a potential type certification process for AWES [3].

Another example appears in the Makani design and engineering reports [4]. In preparation for product certification, the Makani team conducted a preliminary assessment of certification gaps for the Makani Energy Kite with DNV [4]. Figure 5 shows an excerpt from the gap analysis of standards and evaluation aspects of the main AWES wing/aircraft body. For each major component, the relevant wind turbine standard was identified and high-level gaps in the certification approach were identified.

Both examples discussed follow the assumption that AWES certification should use the conventional wind turbine approach, with the gaps for AWES-specific sub-systems and operational risks filled in by aviation standards where appropriate. This general framework is also applied in the present work.

ID	Component	Function	Standard or new aspect	Classifying the problem					Technology Class	Comments	Observations
				Known Application		Technology					
				yes	no	Known	L. hist.	New			
4 Hybrid rotors											
4.1	2.3m Diameter rotor 5 Fixed-Pitch blades	Generate lift for take off and convert wind energy in rotational energy	IEC 61400-1 in combination with DNVGL-ST 0376 for the composite parts		x	x			2		separate blades
4.2	Electro-thermal de-icing	ensures aerodynamic performance and safety relevant	IEC 61400-1 in combination with DNVGL-ST 0076 for electrotechnical systems		x	x			2		Inductive power transfer to avoid slipping
4.3	Lightning protection		IEC 61400-24		x	x			2		Aluminum conductive mesh
4.4	Leading edge erosion protection	extends life time	Aerospace standards	x		x			1	New to Wind industry	Electro-formed nickel
4.5	Hub, shaft and rotor bearing		Machinery Standards, DNVGL-ST-0361	x		x			1		
5 Wings and Platform											
5.1	Wings	Keeps Kite spinning	IEC 61400-1 in combination with, DNVGL-ST-0376 for the composite parts and DNVGL-ST-0361 for machinery components		x	x			2		Loading (see Item 1) and Item 9 (safety factors)
5.2	Pylons	mounting of engine/turbine to the kite	IEC 61400-1 in combination with, DNVGL-ST-0376 for the composite parts and DNVGL-ST-0361 for machinery components		x	x			2		Loading (see Item 1) and Item 9 (safety factors)
5.3	Fuselage	Main body of the kite	IEC 61400-1 in combination with, DNVGL-ST-0376 for the composite parts and DNVGL-ST-0361 for machinery components		x	x			2		Loading (see Item 1) and Item 9 (safety factors)
5.4	Tail plane	Steering and Stability	IEC 61400-1 in combination with, DNVGL-ST-0376 for the composite parts and DNVGL-ST-0361 for machinery components		x	x			2		Loading (see Item 1) and item 9 (safety factors)
5.5	Housing and cut-outs		IEC 61400-1 in combination with, DNVGL-ST-0376 for the composite parts and DNVGL-ST-0361 for machinery components		x	x			2		Loading (see Item 1) and item 9 (safety factors)

Figure 5: Certification gap analysis by DNV for the Makani Energy Kite [4].

3 The Roadmap to Certification

To help create a roadmap for AWES certification, this chapter first outlines the major activities, milestones and the timeline for certification in conventional wind (**Section 3.1**) and civil aviation industries (**Section 3.2**). Finally, the two approaches to certification are contrasted to help identify a roadmap for AWES certification (**Section 3.3**).

3.1 Wind Turbine Certification Process

The wind industry certification scheme requires: (i) **Type Certification** of wind turbines and their components, and (ii) **Project Certification** for the entire wind farm. Figure 6 outlines the application process for wind turbine certification, with the major phases from preliminary design (prior to the certification process) to the maintenance of type and project certificates.

Figure 6: Wind turbine & wind farm certification process (timeline arrows are not to scale).

A **Type Certificate** is the document issued by the certifying body upon successful completion of the process of ensuring that the specific wind turbine type (combination of design, materials, components and manufacturing process) conforms to its specified requirements [5].

A **Project Certificate** is proof of conformity assessment of individual installations of wind turbines or complete wind farms to ensure they meet the necessary standards and technical requirements for safety, reliability, performance, construction and interaction with electrical power networks [6].

A **Prototype Type Certificate** is an optional intermediate step on the path to full type certification that may be relevant to AWES developers. The prototype type certificate establishes and validates a design basis for a system installed in a specific location, like at a test site.

In the wind industry, the IECRE Certification Bodies (RECBs) and IECRE Testing Laboratories (RETLs) are responsible for assessing and granting type and project certificates (Figure 7). RECB and RETL are granted their authority to administer the certification scheme by the IECRE. Customers (turbine integrators) may install their own certified testing facilities (IECRE Customer Test Facilities – RECTF), such as blade mechanical testing facilities [7], with review and approval of the IECRE.

		Certifying Body				Applicant		
		IECRE	RECB	RETL	ISO / Other	Supplier	Integrator	Operator
Product Certificates	Component Certificate		✓	✓		✓		
	Prototype Certificate		✓	✓			✓	
	Type Certificate		✓	✓			✓	
Project Certificates & Approvals	Project Certificate		✓	✓			✓	✓
	IECRE Customer Test Facilities	✓				✓	✓	
	Production Organization Quality Management System				✓	✓	✓	

Figure 7: Responsibilities and approvals in the wind industry.

The organisations producing and assembling components and turbines require ISO 9001 [8] accreditation for their quality management systems. Proof of conformity to ISO 9001 should be granted by a body itself accredited to ISO/IEC 17021 [9] (requirements for bodies providing audit and certification of management systems). Figure 7 also indicates where the responsibility for an application falls to the component supplier, turbine integrator or wind farm operator.

3.2 Civil Aviation Certification Process

Airborne Wind Energy Systems operating today typically fall into the “specific” category of certification for UAS (unmanned aircraft systems). Due to their current size, weight and restricted nature of their operations (often for prototype testing), they do not require full product certification. For large fully commercial AWE systems it is possible their risk category would result in a designation of the “certified” category for certification (Figure 3). This section provides an overview of the full certification process and resulting type certificates and organisational approvals in this scenario. Further analysis of the potential roadmap for AWE systems as they nature and scale is provided in **Section 3.3**.

The civil aviation certification scheme requires: (i) **Type Certification** and **Organisational Approvals** for aircraft design & production, followed by (ii) **Airworthiness Certification** for several organisations. Figure 8 outlines the application process for civil aircraft certification. While civil aviation also uses the **Type Certificate** to designate approval of a specific aircraft product model, the certification scheme includes several additional organisational approvals, these include:

- **Design Organisation Approval (DOA):** recognition that a design organisation is approved to perform design activities within the scope of approval and perform its activities independently from the agency (EASA) [10].
- **Production Organisation Approval (POA):** recognition that a production organisation (e.g. an OEM) can manufacture aircraft to the design approved in the type certificate, allowing the production organisation to issue airworthiness certificates for the aircraft they produce [11].
- **Continuing Airworthiness Organisations:** EASA also manages approvals for maintenance organisation approvals (MOA), maintenance training organisation approvals (MTOA), continuing airworthiness management organisation (CAMO) approvals and combined airworthiness organisation approvals (CAO) [12].

There are also two additional relevant certificates that make up the full picture of aircraft operations:

- **Airworthiness Certificate:** each aircraft produced must obtain an individual airworthiness certificate, indicating that it conforms to the design specified in the type certificate [13].
- **Air Operator Certificate (AOC):** any organisation performing the operations for commercial air transport requires an air operator certificate [14].

Figure 8: Civil aviation certification process (timeline arrows are not to scale).

The aviation industry certifying bodies identified in Figure 9 are the FAA (for the USA), the EASA (for the European Union) and the many remaining national aviation authorities (NAAs). Many NAAs have

co-operation agreements with the FAA, EASA or both agencies, e.g. Transport Canada’s rulemaking co-operation agreement with EASA [15] and technical implementation procedures [16]. These agencies are responsible for granting type certificates, airworthiness certificates and organization approvals.

		Certifying Body			Applicant		
		FAA	EASA	NAA	Supplier	Integrator	Operator
Product Certificates	Component Certificate	✓	✓		✓	✓	
	Type Certificate	✓	✓		✓	✓	
	Design Organisation	✓	✓		✓	✓	
	Production Organisation	✓		✓	✓	✓	
Other Approvals	Combined Airworthiness Organisations	✓	✓	✓			✓
	Air Operator Certificate	✓		✓			✓

Figure 9: Responsibilities and approvals in the civil aviation industry (adapted from [13]).

In the aviation scheme, the objective of organisational approvals like the DOA and POA is to place more of the responsibilities of administration of the certification process in the hands of the integrator. Integrators go through extensive verification processes to ensure they can suitably manage the certification process, with the certifying agency providing review and final sign-off of the type certificate. An organisation requires a DOA before a type certificate can be awarded [13].

Figure 9 also indicates where the responsible applicant for each certificate and organisational approval, i.e. either the component supplier, aircraft integrator or air operator.

3.3 AWES Certification Roadmap

The differences in the two certification schemes seem quite significant (Figure 10); the aviation approach relies heavily on organisational approvals for system design and production, whereas the wind industry requires only a single type certificate. Further in-depth analysis of each type certification process in **Chapter 4**, however, will shed more light on the differences in topics covered by each certification scheme and how well they align.

The project certification approach for the wind industry shares many commonalities with the COA / airworthiness certificate (and the continued airworthiness approval process). Both approaches aim to ensure the long-term reliability, performance and safety of the systems and organisations they apply to.

Figure 10: Organisational approvals in aviation deviate from the wind approach.

The maturity and scale of AWE systems will dictate the aspects of each scheme that are relevant for assessment. Figure 11 maps out how the certification requirements might evolve for AWES as they progress from the current prototype systems to early commercial and fully commercial systems (following the definitions in Figure 3). At each stage of development, the figure considers the wind industry and aviation industry requirements for certification and how they might overlap. For the wind industry it identifies the type certification and project certification requirements. For the aviation industry, the figure addresses the type certification, organisational approvals and risk category.

The “regulatory sandbox” currently used by today’s AWES developers involves conducting a SORA (specific operations risk assessment) for each specific AWES installation and obtaining a permit to fly from the relevant national aviation authority.

Figure 11: Comparing the certification requirements between wind and aviation industries for AWES as they mature to fully commercial systems (WT = Wind Turbine, CA = Civil Aviation).

There has been some recent progress with NAAs approving permits to fly based on prior permits authorised in other European countries without requiring a full redetermination and assessment, e.g.

Kitepower's cross-border permit from The Netherlands to Ireland to fly at the Bangor Erris test centre [17]. Continued cross-jurisdiction approval should improve the speed and predictability of AWES deployment for the prototype and early commercial systems.

The roadmap to deploying large numbers of commercial systems, however, will require investment in type certification and likely project certification as a means of ensuring financing and the bankability of AWES projects. For the pre-commercial and early commercial systems in Figure 11 the limited prototype or restricted type certificates may be sufficient, while for fully commercial systems full type certification of one form or another may then be necessary. However the exact path to certification remains uncertain.

4 AWES Aerostructures Type Certification Analysis

This chapter aims to identify the similarities in the overall type certification process for conventional wind turbines and aircraft (**Section 4.1**). Focusing on the relevant standards that form the design basis for the composite airframe components in an AWES, **Section 4.2** sets out the relevant standards and guidance materials from both industries. **Section 4.3** then lays out a methodology for comparing the two industries' approaches to certifying composite parts and for finding the gaps related to AWES design. Finally, **Section 4.4** presents the results of an example gap analysis, and highlights areas for future in-depth analysis in the standards.

4.1 Type Certification Process Comparison

Figure 12 shows the steps in the wind turbine type certification process [5], from design basis evaluation to final evaluation and ongoing certification maintenance. Each step produces conformity statements upon its completion.

Figure 12: Wind turbine Type Certification process.

Overall, similar steps are followed in the phases of aviation type certification [18] process, outlined in Figure 13. The initial step in both processes (*Design Basis Evaluation* and *Working Methods Definition*) serves similar functions, to ensure the design methods and basis for certification evaluation to be used follow best practice and meet the expected threshold for assessment.

Similarly, the second step for each industry (*Design Basis Evaluation* and *Certification Basis Definition*) cover the design definition and engineering evaluations of each system.

Figure 13: Civil Aviation Type Certification process.

At this point the two certification processes diverge. Following the wind industry approach, the next steps involve evaluating the manufacturing process, testing of the functionality of the turbine and its sub-systems and final evaluation for conformance of the turbine type before granting of the Type Certificate.

In the aviation industry, the next steps are to define the certification programme and demonstrate its compliance. The separate production organisation approval (POA) allows the aircraft integrator to manage the manufacturing process and system/sub-system evaluation activities.

Figure 14: Type Certification processes compared.

While there are differences in the overall process, a gap analysis between the two industries requires a deeper inspection of the first two steps in each type certification process, as highlighted in Figure 14. The design basis and working methods defined in these steps include the standards, specifications and means of compliance for the design, manufacturing and continued operation/maintenance of AWES components.

4.2 Relevant Aerostructures Standards & Guidance Materials

The wind turbine certification procedure outlined by OD-501 [5] provides a concise list of the topics covered by the design basis evaluation process step and is illustrated in Figure 15. For the remainder of this chapter, the wind turbine certification process will be used as the basis for assessing gaps in AWES certification.

Figure 15: Elements of the Design Basis Evaluation process.

Identifying the design standards relating to the fibre-reinforced composite wind turbine rotor blades is the starting point for an analysis of the gaps in AWES composite aerostructures certification. Table 1 provides a list of the wind turbine standards relating to the composite blade that address the eight topics in the design basis evaluation.

For comparison, the table also lists relevant certification specifications and acceptable means of compliance documents for composite aircraft components. The airworthiness considerations in AMC 20-29 can be used to address the gaps for components and functionalities that simply do not appear in the wind turbine standards, such as the design of control surface like ailerons, or the integration of landing gear into the airframe structure.

Table 1: Comparing relevant technical standards and certification specifications for composite components in wind and aviation applications.

Wind Turbine Technical Standards	Aviation Technical Standards
IEC 61400-1 Design Requirements	CS-23 Normal-Category Aeroplanes
IEC 61400-2 Small Wind Turbines	AMC 20-29 Composite Aircraft Structure
IEC 61400-3 Design Requirements for Offshore Wind Turbines	6. Material and Fabrication Development
IEC 61400-5 Wind Turbine Blades	7. Proof of Structure – Static
IEC 61400-13 Measurement of Mechanical Loads	8. Proof of Structure – Fatigue and Damage Tolerance
IEC 61400-23 Full-Scale Structural Testing of Rotor Blades	9. Continued Airworthiness
IEC 61400-24 Lightning Protection	11. Additional Considerations (Crashworthiness, Fire Protection & Lightning Protection)
DNVGL-ST-0376 Rotor Blades for Wind Turbines	

Looking at the design evaluation process step in Figure 16 provides a view into the applicability of the wind turbine standards for AWES, and where AMC 20-29 can begin to fill the gaps. In the design evaluation step, the analysis and documentation for all the system and sub-system designs are assessed. This includes the control system for the turbine, the expected loading envelopes, the mechanical, structural and electrical sub-systems, as well as the processes for manufacturing and installation of the device.

Figure 16 shows where the rotor blade standards must be replaced with standards related to the aerostructures of an AWES (the main wing, control surfaces, fuselage, tail, etc.) and where new sub-systems should be added to the list, such as the propulsion system.

When considering the composite components, some new sub-systems can be particularly impactful. For example, large, localised heating around the propulsion system can have a significant impact on composite primary structures, requiring selection of a suitable temperature resistant matrix material. In the cases of these new sub-systems and components that commonly appear in aircraft, the aviation technical standards should be referred to.

There are also areas of significant overlap between the wind and aviation standards, which require careful evaluation of both schemes to ensure all operational requirements are considered, these include the manufacturing, transportation, installation and maintenance requirements for composite components as identified in Figure 16. A process for evaluating the gaps and overlap between these technical documents is outlined in the next section.

Figure 16: Elements of the Design Evaluation process (some of the modifications required to topics relating to composites in this step are highlighted).

4.3 Gap Analysis Methodology

The next step is to examine the specific paragraphs in the two industries’ certification documents to identify the similarities and the gaps. Figure 17 shows an example of the approach, where initially common sections are highlighted between the documents. For the wind industry, the example shows the tables of contents of the IEC 61400-1 wind turbine design standard [19], and the DNVGL-ST-0376 wind turbine design standard document [20]. For the aviation industry, the tables of contents for CS-23 [21] and AMC 20-29 [22] are both shown.

The blue boxes highlight the sections/chapters in each document where the topic “composite structures analysis and design” is addressed. This process can be used to map the topics covered between each standard and to identify high-level gaps in the wind standards for AWE systems design.

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Figure 17: Identifying the common sections and topics between the wind and aviation industries' standards and certification documentation.

Taking the mapping approach to the next level, the specific paragraphs in each standard can be identified for topics of interest. Figure 18 shows the paragraphs in the four certification materials that relate to the definition of composite material processing requirements.

Once the relevant paragraphs and sections have been identified for a particular topic, the paragraphs can be compared and the applicability of each industry’s guidance to AWE systems design can be assessed.

Figure 18: Mapping paragraphs related to the topic “material processing requirements” between the two industries’ certification materials.

4.4 Example Aerostructures Gap Analysis

Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 demonstrate a gap analysis for three sample topics related to composite aerostructures design: composite structures design methods, environmental effects on composites and design of structural components, respectively.

For the three topics, a summary of each paragraph from the four certification materials is provided, then the gaps are identified in the wind industry standards relating to aerostructure design, and any additional considerations specific to AWE systems are also documented.

Where aspects of the following topics diverge considerably from both the wind and civil aviation standards, it is noted that a new AWE-specific technical standard may be necessary. The definition of the relevant paragraphs in such a new standard can draw the relevant elements from existing wind and aviation standards.

Table 2: Example gap analysis for a fatigue evaluation methodology between wind industry design standards and aviation industry certification specifications/accepted means of compliance.

Topic	Wind Standards		Aviation Standards	
	IEC 61400-1	DNVGL-ST-0376	CS-23	AMC 20-29
Fatigue evaluation: fatigue evaluation methodology	Section 7.6.3: Requires the use of an appropriate fatigue damage calculation methodology (e.g. Miner’s rule), with guidance on partial safety factors to be applied for fatigue.	Section 2.5.3: Provides guidance on various partial reduction factors applied for the case of fibre failure of the composite components.	CS 23.2240: Requires that means are applied to prevent any structural failures due to foreseeable causes of strength degradation, that could result in failures or fatal injuries, or extended periods of operation with reduced safety margins.	Paragraph 8.b: Substantiation of fatigue is recommended through tests, or analysis supported by tests, at coupon, sub-component and component scales. The structure’s damage tolerance is considered in Paragraph 8.a with the definition of allowable damage growth.

Wind Standards Gaps

The wind standard uses an approach to fatigue evaluation based on material knock-down factors and damage accumulation assessment based on coupon testing.

The aviation standard describes a more stringent damage tolerant design approach requiring testing at coupon, sub-component and component level to ensure failures do not occur during the service life of the aircraft.

AWES Design Considerations

The methods of fatigue design / analysis should relate to the risk assessment of the overall AWE system, and the resulting safety requirements for the composite aerostructures.

An evaluation of the duty cycles of the AWE system, combined with the results of the SORA (specific operations risk assessment) may provide an initial estimate to the risk profile from fatigue failure in composite components.

The selection of fatigue / damage evaluation method should ensure the safe operation of the AWE system composite components for their entire lifecycle, accounting for extreme operation and any maintenance, repair or replacement strategies.

Table 3: Example gap analysis for the effects of temperature on composite structures between wind industry design standards and aviation industry certification specifications/accepted means of compliance.

Topic	Wind Standards		Aviation Standards	
	IEC 61400-1	DNVGL-ST-0376	CS-23	AMC 20-29
Environmental conditions: temperature effects	Sections 6.4.1 & 6.4.2: Defines normal and extreme operational temperature ranges (-10°C to +40°C) for the wind turbine.	Section 2.1.2: Defines the process for setting the envelope of temperatures structures are exposed to.	CS 23.2260 section (e): Requires that thermal effects must be determined if they have a significant effect on a critical component or structure.	Paragraph 6.d: Provides a general description of environmental exposure conditions for temperature and humidity.

Wind Standards Gaps

AMC 20-29 notes additional considerations for peak temperatures due to on-board systems that generate heat (e.g. engines, batteries, or electronics).

AWES Design Considerations

The wind standards consider the normal and extreme environmental temperature ranges for wind turbine design. Since components near additional thermal sources (like propulsion systems) may be present in AWE systems, a dedicated technical standard for AWE systems should include this design consideration.

Table 4: Example gap analysis for the design of the tether attachment interface between wind industry design standards and aviation industry certification specifications/accepted means of compliance.

Topic	Wind Standards		Aviation Standards	
	IEC 61400-1	DNVGL-ST-0376	CS-23	AMC 20-29
Design of structural components: tether attachment interface	-	Section 2.2.2: Documentation requirements of the design assumptions and parameters for the blade root attachment interface.	CS 23.2250: General description of the requirements for design data, and the suitability of design details.	Paragraph 6.g: Describes the process for identifying design values for individual components, with a focus on structural damage due to impact.

Wind Standards Gaps

The greater number of components, and the larger variation in the design of aircraft systems, result in more generic guidelines for component design and verification in the civil aviation documents. These are more appropriate to follow for relevant design features than wind standards.

AWES Design Considerations

There is no direct analogue in a conventional wind turbine to the tether attachment interface for an AWE system. The closest comparable design feature in the wind standards is the blade root attachment interface.

Similarly in conventional aircraft design there is no tether attachment interface. However, the general descriptions for determining design values for components in aircraft are referenced in Table 4. These considerations may be used as the basis for crafting a new paragraph in a dedicated AWE technical standard on the topic of tether attachment interfaces.

5 Conclusions

5.1 Summary

This document provides an overview of the certification schemes for wind turbines and civil aircraft and describes in detail the type certification process for conventional wind turbine systems. Documenting the topics covered by wind turbine type certification provides insights into the high-level gaps in the wind certification scheme as it would relate to AWE systems.

This document also provides a framework for assessing the technical differences between the two industries' approaches to composite structures design and manufacturing (or more generally applied, it could also be used as a means of analysing any other design aspect of these systems for certification). The framework could be used by original equipment manufacturers, component suppliers, engineering consultants or regulatory bodies to assess the certification requirements of AWE systems.

The framework was used on three example topics related to aerostructures certification: choice of fatigue evaluation methodology, temperature effects on composite materials and the design of the blade root attachment. For each topic, any gaps in the wind turbine standards as they relate to AWES were identified, and a summary of considerations for AWE system developers was provided.

If AWE system certification is to follow the IECRE process, then the framework presented can be used to identify any gaps in the existing set of design standards, and to ensure that the aviation standards are considered wherever appropriate.

5.2 Next steps

With the certification roadmap and the presented framework in mind, several activities could follow on from this project to continue advancing the topic of airborne wind energy certification:

- Continue further assessment of AWES certification, for example, by applying the framework from **Chapter 4** to mapping existing standards suitable to AWE sub-systems and components.
- Continue this research in a collaborative environment with key industry stakeholders (aviation authorities, standardisation experts, AWES developers, wind farm developers) on a regular basis, to incorporate findings from the early testing and demonstration systems into data-based recommendations for future standards and certification.
- Disseminate the certification roadmap assessment to groups in the AWE community working on standardization, e.g. IEA Wind Task 48 on Airborne Wind Energy.
- Support sub-system and component certification research for composite aerostructures design and manufacturing, including requirements definition and standards assessment via dedicated working groups.
- Support education and training activities on certification for AWE companies as they move towards greater levels of commercial readiness.

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